

Different Approaches for Software Project Management in Academics Environment.

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Abstract

Software project management is a sub-discipline of project management in which software projects are planned, monitored and controlled. This paper describes a new way of educating student in which syllabus is framed after considering the alumni had to face while learning them techniques as part of their Industrial training where there are different challenges like time, travel and work pressures. In this paper we have discuss an effective process structure software project management to teach the software project management within an academic environment.

Keywords: Software project management, Software development process, Unified modeling language, globalization. Software Process, Integration, Requirement.

1. Introduction

The software project management course includes structured project management, Object oriented project management, Web engineering project management, Global project management. In this globalization time the development of new software increasingly, is a focal point of competition. The objective of software project management is to produce quality software products to satisfy user needs within scheduled time and at acceptable costs. To do so, project manager and their entire team must be trained to be able to make decisions involving trade-off

The remaining of this paper is organized as follows: section 2 explains the background of SPM and related work. Section 3 explains industrial training process. Section 4 explains Academics teaching model with related to industrial project. Section 5 provides an overview of UML Case study diagrams of SPM for security model and we Conclude and Future in section 6.

2. Background

2.1 Academic software project

Teaching in collages their activities of software project management do not provide enough conditions for the students to develop a real project. If the students lack the background of project practice, they understand only the theories, not the real substance. To make the students understand and master this curriculum 'practice teaching' is put in the front of software project management teaching. The industrial training as well as structure and content of industrial workshop for software project management in academic course is necessary.

2.2 Comparison between actual industrial and academic software project management

- i. Topical content of both industrial project and the academic course project is similar.
- ii. Major difference between the industrial workshop in which software project management was taught in 5-6 day and the academic course lasting a full semester, was that the academic version allowed time between sessions for extensive reading by the participants.
- iii. In the academic environment all planning needed to be done before the start of the semesters, but details of cases, lectures and handouts could be changed easily between classes to respond to interests of students and the experiences of the instructor with students during the early parts of the course

3. Industrial training process.

3.1 Objective of industrial training: Industrial training is imported in a workshop of 8 to 10 days. The objectives developed by the workshop staff, based on the survey, interviews, a literature search and personal experience was: a) Describe underlying business and technical processes b) Identify the requirements for successfully initiating & operating a new project. C) Manage the scope, schedule and cost of a project. D) Build a strong team of employees, partners and suppliers. E) Keep management, customers and team members informed of status. F) Address risks in a logical way and avoid common pitfalls. G) Direct the integration of multiple projects in an organization or program.

3.2 Structure of industrial training: It contains two parts a)Part I has to do For experience Participant b)Part II has to do for un experience participant

3.2.1 For experience Participant: This type of participant has to do introductory exercise in the full sequence lectures, exercises, audit project, present audit, retrospective lecture and retrospective exercise

3.2.2 For un experience participant: This type of participant has to do introductory exercise in sequence lectures, develop project, prepare of presentation, present review, present audit feedback, retrospective lecture and retrospective exercise

3.2.3 Participant has to attend lectures on the full topics related to Software project management: Introduction, Perspective, Planning, Estimation, High Performance Team-Organization structures, teambuilding and conflict resolution, Audit and Reviews, Risk Management, Partners and Vendors, Managing Multiple Projects

4.1 Training Goal: Software project management aims at training the students' abilities of SPM and control, and qualifying them to cooperate and create. During the actual training process, it's important to show the students abilities of cooperating, learning, communicating, expressing and leading. After studying this curriculum, the students should have the following abilities such as processes, software specifications, effective cost budget and control, plan of the software

development cycle, efficiently, resources of all the departments, controlling software quality, adjustments when mistakes come up, track and summarize the development progress

4.2 Training Model: The advanced teaching idea of “Learning by doing” is introduced in the teaching activities, which in notates the traditional cramming teaching model. In the new teaching activities, one teacher is in charge of 20 students who are divided into several teams and would implement an actual industrial project.

4.3 Teaching Case: Our teacher’s offer requirements of some industrial projects they have finished for students and the students could focus on the project management. The systems requirements provided by the teachers include social insurance application, traffic charge application, and decision support application of social insurance

4.4 Teaching Process: The students implement the applications according to the software engineering in the experimental classes or their spare time. While the teachers impart the knowledge related to SPM according to the students’ development in the class. The students are required to finish some management tasks and hand in these phase achievements. The implemented systems by the students are submitted in the late semester.

4.5 Teaching Content : It contain Report for approval of proposal , Effort estimation, Project planning, List of ten risks, Final report

4.6 Team organization: Each person could be the manager of the team in different tasks. Many problems are resulted from insufficient communication, which has something with characters, not technology or ability

4.7 Assessment methods: It doesn’t take place after the experiments, while it does exist in the teaching process. There are three assessment parts: experiments assessment, final project assessment and final oral defense.

4.8 Benefits of following this model: It could encourage the students to finish this curriculum; on the other hand it could let the students know his study result, his advantages and disadvantages, which would benefit the future application and study of software project management.

5. UML diagram of SPM of security model draw as part of software project management.

The emergence of UML has been well documented. UML is a modelling language - not a process. In a course related to system analysis it is not sufficient to simply model different views of a system - the students require a framework in which to see how the models intermesh to aid the transition from statement of requirements to high level design.

Figure 2. Use case diagram for security model

Figure 2 use case diagram show total system security context diagram in which there are different actor such as database, devices and administrator which control over system of securities. In this security module it provides port no, IP address, and connection of internet.

Figure 3 security user enters their IP address which will be accepted boundary component that communication with an end user of the system .An entity component represents domain of entity. And service components provide a layer of services that communicate between boundary components and entity components.

Figure 3. Sequence diagram for security model

6. Conclusion and Future:

In this paper we have presented that there is better opportunity for true education of software project management in the academic environment than there was in the industrial environment where time, travel and work pressures shape the workshop into a form of what could be considered training as opposed to education. We should realize that the theory must be combined with practice. We have also suggested Industrial project teaching model of SPM based on the idea of “learning by doing practice” that focuses on learning professional knowledge from applications

7. Reference:

- [1] Applied Software Project Management, Jennifer Greene, Andrew Stellman.
- [2] Software Engineering, Roger S. Pressman.
- [3] Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge, Project Management Institute.1994.
- [4] Thayer, Richard, Software Engineering Project Management, IEEE computer Society, 1997.
- [5] UML design and concept, Rumbaugh.
- [6] Global software development. *IEEE Software*, 18(2):16–20, 2001.

